

Effects of the skew angle of conical bits on bit temperature, bit wear, and rock cutting performance

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1. INTRODUCTION

Understanding the contact mechanism between a cutting tool and rock is important in mining, drilling, and tunneling industries as the physical contact can cause frictional ignition and bit wear. The heat generated in the rock cutting process can be a precursor to frictional ignition, which can potentially ignite methane (CH₄) gas, leading to explosions as occurred in the 2010 explosion at the Upper Big Branch Mine in West Virginia [1, 2]. Therefore, friction mitigation is critical for improving mining safety [3].

Additionally, understanding the bit wear is crucial for preventing financial losses and saving project budgets by reducing bit replacement. Many factors are taken into account in cutting tool wear as the physical contact mechanism between a tool and rock varies with the properties of the rock, tool, and working conditions (cutting speed, line spacing, depth of cut, etc.), significantly affecting the bit wear process [4]. Previous studies have reported the importance of predicting operational circumstances related to the wear rate of cutting tools [5]. In addition, other studies demonstrated that tool wear typically is mainly determined by the mechanical and thermal interactions that occur between a tool and rock [6]. Some theories have been further developed to account for the bluntness of the tool [7]. Some of the main parameters in these theories are the cutting geometry parameters such as the cutting depth and the angles of the cutting tools [8, 9].

31 However, not much work has been reported in quantifying the relationship between wear and
32 cutting machine performance.

33 Skew angle is an important parameter when cutting materials such as rock, wood, and metal
34 [10]. Many researchers have studied the effect of the skew angle of conical bits on bit rotation
35 because understanding the bit rotation is important for extending bit life. Bit rotation can allow
36 the bit to maintain its shape and can even re-sharpen the tip [2, 11-16]. The skew angle in rock
37 cutting is defined as the angle between the projection of the bit axis on rock surface and the line
38 of cut. However, in contrast to the number of studies done on bit rotation, very few studies on
39 skew angle have been reported regarding friction mitigation and bit wear [16], even though
40 understanding the effects of skew angle on frictional ignition and bit wear are critical for
41 workplace safety and productivity.

42 The skew angle of conical bits can significantly change the physical contact mechanism
43 between a tool and rock, affecting bit temperature, bit wear, and rock cutting performance. In a
44 previous study [16], the effect of skew angle on bit temperature increment was tested with four
45 bit types of different weights. Bit weight can influence the physical contact between a tool and
46 rock by changing the normal, cutting, thrust, side, and shear forces. For this reason, in this paper
47 four bit types with the same weight were used to investigate the effects of skew angle on rock
48 cutting performance. Thus, our results demonstrate the effects of skew angle more precisely
49 without contributions from bit weight.

50 In this study, we explored the effects of skew angle not only on the temperature of bit tips (as
51 a function of the tip surface area) but also on bit wear and rock cutting performance. The results
52 of this study provide insightful information for designing cutting bits with safer and more wear-
53 tolerant shapes, significantly contributing to improving the safety and productivity in the mining
54 and tunneling industries.

55

56 **2. MATERIALS AND METHODS**

57 ***2.1. Design and fabrication of the testing machine***

58 An advanced rock friction machine was designed and fabricated (Fig. 1). In the advanced
59 cutting machine, the steel base frame was installed to reduce the amount of vibration throughout
60 the machine while it was running. A granite rock wheel (10" in diameter) on the friction machine
61 was prepared with a water jet machine. The granite wheel was mounted on a shaft equipped with

62 heavy-duty ball bearings as previously described [16]. The rock friction machine was designed
63 by considering the three critical angles – clearance, contact, and skew angle – in Figure 2 as
64 described. For a continuous miner or longwall shearer, the rotation axis is the centerline of the
65 cutting drum. For each cutting test, a cutting bit was mounted in the bit housing on the lever arm.
66 The housing was rotated to adjust the skew angle of the bit, and a protractor like gauge aided in
67 absolute precision when measuring the skew angle (Fig. 1). Tests were performed at skew angles
68 of 0°, 6°, 12°, and 18°.

69

70 **2.2. Engineering of cutting tools**

71 The weight of four bit types (S1, S2, B1, and B2) used in the previous study varied from
72 558.8–1,133.2 g [16]. To more precisely assess skew angle effects on bit wear, rock excavation
73 performance, and bit temperature than in that previous study, each of the four bit types was
74 machined with the same weight because bit weight can significantly affect normal, cutting, shear,
75 side, and thrust forces (Fig. 3 and Table 1). Because the weight of S1 was the lightest (~ 539 g),
76 all bits were machined to ~539 g (± 2 g of deviation) (Table 1).

77

78 **2.3. Experiment, data collection, and analysis**

79 The granite wheel was mounted on the rock cutting machine, and the cutting bit was placed
80 near the top of the rock wheel at a specific skew angle. The rock cutting test was performed
81 under ~ 672 m min⁻¹ of cutting speed for 5 min, and the depth of cut after the experiment was ~ 2
82 mm. The rock cutting was performed with a single bit for each test, so line spacing was not
83 applicable in this study. Water was not applied during the cutting tests to examine the effect of
84 skew angle on bit temperature without interference from water cooling effect. The bit
85 temperature was recorded with a 50-Hz infrared (IR) camera to estimate the temperature of the
86 bits. A full set of tests was performed with four bit types of the same weight, 4 different skew
87 angles (0° to 18° in 6° steps), and 6 repetitions for each condition. To avoid the artificial
88 increases in bit temperature due to successive friction tests, after each test the tested rock wheel
89 and cutting bit were replaced with a cool-downed rock wheel and bit ($\sim 25^\circ$). Data were analyzed
90 with programs specific to the IR camera used (Fig. 4). Bit wear and rock excavation performance
91 were estimated from the loss of bit and rock weights, so bit and rock weights were measured
92 before and after each of the tests.

93

94 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

95 In this paper, we examined the effects of skew angle on bit temperature, bit wear, and rock
96 cutting performance. Each cutting test was performed for 5 min with four bit types of the same
97 weight (S1, S2, B1, and B2) but different tip surface areas (Table 1). The results obtained from
98 the cutting tests and their interpretations are described below.

99

100 ***3.1. Skew angle effects on bit temperature***

101 After the 5 min cutting test, bit temperature was monitored with an IR camera to understand
102 the effect of skew angle on bit temperature. An effect of skew angle on bit temperature was only
103 observed in bit B2, which had the largest bit tip surface area. In particular, the bit temperature of
104 B2 at a 12° skew angle was ~23.5% higher when compared to the control condition (at a 0° skew
105 angle) (Fig. 5D). The results support the conclusion that the skew angle increases the surface
106 contact area between the bit tip and rock wheel, causing an increase of friction energy [16].
107 However, no significant effect of skew angle was observed in S1, S2, and B1 (Fig. 5A–5C). This
108 evidence indicates that the effect of skew angle on bit temperature is relatively greater when the
109 bit tip surface area is larger.

110 Interestingly, in our previous study, the effect of skew angle on bit temperature was observed
111 in S2 and B1 [16], whereas the skew angle effect of S2 and B1 was not observed in the current
112 study. This difference can be explained with the reduction of bit weights used in the current
113 experiment. In this paper, unlike the previous study, we machined all bits with the same weight
114 (539 g, ± 2 g) to more precisely assess the skew angle effects of four bit types without
115 contribution from bit weights. Conversely, the weight of the bits used in the previous study was
116 variable from 558.8–1,133.2 g [16]. In particular, the weights of S2, B1, and B2 used in the
117 previous study were much heavier than those used in the current study, suggesting that the skew
118 angle effect on bit temperature can be enhanced by increasing bit weight.

119 Also, noticeably, the negative correlation between bit tip surface area and bit temperature
120 (after the 5 min cutting tests) is observed at the various skew angles (Fig. 6). This suggests that
121 the bit temperature of tips with a larger surface area was less than the temperature of the tips with
122 smaller surface area. It is likely that the large surface area tips can dissipate heat faster than the
123 small area tips regardless of applied skew angles. Thus, the skew angle effect on bit temperature

124 is greater when the bit tip surface area is larger (Fig. 5), while the actual temperature of bits is
125 higher when bit tip surface area is smaller (Fig. 6).

126 In our previous study [16], the negative correlation between bit tip surface area and bit
127 temperature was observed after a 3 min cutting test. However, we could not attribute the negative
128 effect of tip surface area on bit temperature as we could not rule out the bit weight effect because
129 the weights of four bit types were different from one another. In this study, because bits of the
130 same weight were used in the tests, the effect of bit weight on bit temperature can be ruled out.
131 Thus, the results of this study strongly support the evidence for the negative correlation between
132 bit tip surface area and bit temperature during the cutting tests.

133 Remarkably, we demonstrated experimentally that temperatures higher than 537°C were
134 generated by the friction between a conical bit and rock during the rock cutting tests (Fig. 7).
135 This was observed only in S1: the bit with the smallest tip surface area (Table 1). Because the
136 auto ignition temperature of methane is 537°C [17], any temperature higher than 537°C can be
137 potentially dangerous in practical mining processes. Thus, based on our results, we propose to
138 use cutting tools that have a large tip surface area to avoid generating high bit temperatures,
139 especially considering that in the workplace methane gas is present. Additionally, our results
140 support the evidence that high temperatures can develop on the surface of a cutting tool due to
141 heat energy generated by friction between the tool and rock [3, 6]. Thus, it is important to
142 understand the parameters that affect the amount of friction generated between a tool and rock.
143 Our findings, therefore, provide insights into how to advance cutting tool design and shape.

144

145 ***3.2. Skew angle effects on bit wear***

146 The effect of the skew angle on cutting tool wear was examined by measuring the reduced bit
147 weight after the 5 min cutting tests. The weight loss of B2 was significantly reduced by ~192%
148 at a 12° skew angle when compared with a 0° skew angle (Fig. 8D). This result indicates the
149 substantial effect of skew angle on bit wear. Although we do not fully understand the underlying
150 mechanism of how skew angle and physical contact area reduced B2 wear, the observation can
151 be explained by a reduction of shear forces between a tool and rock at higher skew angles,
152 resulting in the reduction of bit wear. In contrast, no significant effect of skew angle on bit wear
153 was observed in B1 and S2, which both had smaller tip surface areas than did B2 (Fig. 8). The

154 results support the conclusion that the skew angle effect on the reduction of bit wear is greater
155 when the tip surface area is large.

156 Unexpectedly, a significant skew angle effect on bit wear was observed in S1, which had the
157 smallest tip surface area among the four bit types. After the 5-min cutting test, the weight of S1
158 was significantly reduced by ~57% at an 18° skew angle when compared with a 0° skew angle
159 (Fig. 8A). Because the skew angle effect on bit wear is greater when tip surface area is large as
160 shown in S2, B1, and B2, this result is currently not fully understood. However, it is noticeable
161 that the tip angle of S1 is much narrower than other bits used in the cutting tests (Table 1). Thus,
162 it is reasonable to suppose that tip angle is another critical determinant of skew angle effect on
163 bit wear.

164 The wear of rock cutting bits can be significantly affected by the sliding and impact motion
165 at the interface between a tool and rock [18]. In our experiment, the sliding mechanism is a main
166 factor contributing to bit wear. Sliding motions can induce four wear mechanisms: abrasion,
167 adhesion, surface fatigue, and tribo-chemical reaction [19]. Surface fatigue and tribo-chemical
168 reaction commonly occur when the rate of wear is low, and adhesive wear occurs when the
169 temperature and stress are high (rendering them inapplicable using our experiment conditions).
170 Thus, abrasion wear is assumed to dominate the wear process in our rock cutting tests. Abrasion
171 wear can be classified into four types of material failure: micro-cutting, micro-fatigue, micro-
172 ploughing, and micro-cracking [20]. In general, micro-ploughing, micro-cutting, and micro-
173 fatigue are the material failures that occur predominately in ductile materials such as steel
174 whereas micro-cracking is a dominant type of material failure mainly observed in brittle
175 materials such as tungsten carbide (WC). As the tip of cutting tools used in the tests is WC,
176 micro-cracking including micro-spalling, WC particle pullout and extrusion of binding metal
177 seems to be a main mechanism of material failure, resulting in bit wear of our cutting tests [21].
178 However, the effect of tip angle with changes in skew angle on bit wear remain to be understood,
179 so future work will focus on understanding the effect of skew angle on micro-cracking and
180 micro-spalling with different cutting tools at various tip angles.

181

182 ***3.3. Skew angle effect on rock cutting performance***

183 To examine the effect of skew angle on rock cutting performance, the reduction of rock
184 weight was measured before and after the 5 min cutting tests. In B2, the rock weight was

185 significantly reduced up to ~121% at a 12° skew angle compared with a 0° skew angle (Fig. 9D).
186 The result supports the evidence for a skew angle effect on rock excavation performance.
187 Additionally, the results suggest a positive correlation between bit wear and rock cutting
188 performance: when more rock is excavated, more bit wear occurs (Fig. 8D and 9D). In contrast
189 to B2, the skew angle effect on rock cutting performance was insignificant in S2 and B1. This
190 result is quite consistent with the skew angle effect on bit wear as shown in S2 and B1 (no
191 significant effect). Furthermore, the effects of skew angle on the reduction of both rock weight
192 loss and bit wear are greater when the bit tip surface area is larger (Fig. 8 and 9).

193 Additionally, a skew angle effect on the reduction of rock weight was observed in S1. After
194 the 5 min cutting tests with S1, the rock weight significantly reduced up to ~52% at an 18° skew
195 angle when compared with a 0° skew angle (Fig. 9D). Consequently, using a greater skew angle
196 in S1 could reduce rock cutting performance with a reduction of the bit wear. As S1 has the
197 narrowest tip angle among the four bit types, the effects of tip angle on rock cutting performance
198 also need to be understood. Although to date it is not clear how the tip angle of a cutting tool
199 affects rock cutting performance, the tip angle can influence the surface contact mechanism
200 between a tool and rock, especially affecting the physical contact area. Future work will
201 therefore include investigating the surface contact mechanism between a tool and rock with
202 varying bit tip angles.

203 The correlation between bit wear and rock cutting performance was examined at the four
204 different skew angles. The R^2 value between bit wear and rock weight loss was relatively high in
205 S1 (0.88) and B2 (0.91) whereas the value in S2 (0.11) and B1 (0.004) was less. Similar to the
206 correlation results, the effects of skew angle on bit wear and rock weight loss were significant in
207 S1 and B2, but not in S2 and B1 (Fig. 10). The results suggest that the skew angle of a cutting
208 tool can affect the strength of the correlation between bit wear and rock weight loss, and it is
209 dependent upon the bit tip surface area and skew angle. However, the statistical significance of
210 the correlation between bit wear and rock weight loss cannot be determined with the R^2 value as
211 the R^2 value only can represent the strength of the correlation between two variables. Instead, a
212 p-value obtained with regression analysis was used to determine the statistical significance.
213 Based on the p-value ($p < 0.05$), a significant correlation between bit wear and rock weight loss
214 was observed in B2, but not in S1, S2, and B1. Interestingly, the R^2 value (0.88) in S1 is
215 relatively high, but the correlation in S1 is insignificant as the p-value is greater than 0.05.

216 Additionally, it is noticeable that the effects of skew angle on bit temperature, bit wear, and
217 rock weight loss were significant only in B2, supporting the conclusion that skew angle effects
218 are greater when bit tip surface area is large. Based on the results, we propose to use cutting bits
219 having large tip surface areas when studying skew angle effects on bit wear, rock cutting
220 performance, bit temperature, and other related mechanisms. Thus, our results obtained from
221 rock cutting tests provide insightful information for improving cutting tool design and
222 technology. In the future, cutting speed, depth of cut, line spacing, and rock physical
223 characteristics other than skew angle may have significant impacts on rock cutting performance,
224 our further work will focus on these parameters to provide useful information for practical
225 applications.

226

227 **4. CONCLUSIONS**

228 Understanding the effects of skew angle on bit temperature, bit wear, and rock excavation
229 performance are critical to improve the workplace safety and the cost effectiveness of the
230 excavation process in the mining and tunneling industries. The rock cutting and friction ignition
231 processes between a cutting tool and a rock wheel were examined with a bench-scale device. The
232 main findings of this study are as follows: (1) skew angle effect on temperature was significant
233 in B2 (large tip surface area); (2) bit tip surface area was negatively related to bit tip temperature
234 during the cutting tests; (3) bit wear of B2 and S1 was significantly reduced at a certain skew
235 angle when compared with a 0° skew angle, suggesting that tip angle and tip surface area are
236 related to skew angle effect on bit wear; and (4) a significant positive correlation between bit
237 wear and rock weight loss was observed only in B2. The results support the conclusions that
238 skew angle effects on bit temperature, bit wear, and rock excavation performance are greater
239 when bit tip surface area is large. The results of this study will be useful for cutting bit
240 technology, contributing significantly to improving workplace safety and cost effectiveness.

241

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- 292

293 **Table legend**

294

295 **Table 1.** The weight, tip angle, and tip surface area of engineered cutting tools used in the experiment. All
296 bits were engineered to 539 g within ± 2 g of deviation. The values of the bit tip angle and the tip surface
297 area were obtained from our previous paper (Kim 2015).

298

299 **Figure legends**

300

301 **Figure 1.** The frictional ignition test machine with the rock wheel (A) and the protractor such as gage aid
302 (B). The skew angle of the cutting tools was adjusted using the protractor such as gage aid.

303

304 **Figure 2.** Cartoon images for the critical angles of a cutting bit. A: initial clearance angle, B: attack angle,
305 and C: skew angle.

306

307 **Figure 3.** Engineered conical cutting bits within ± 2 g of deviation. B1: BETEK coal cutting bit; B2:
308 BETEK rock cutting bit; S1: Sandvik coal cutting bit; and S2: Sandvik rock cutting bit. Unit is millimeter
309 (mm).

310

311 **Figure 4.** Snapshot image obtained with IR data processing program.

312

313 **Figure 5.** The effect of skew angle on bit temperature after the 5 min of friction tests. *: significantly
314 different from zero (0) skew angle at $P < 0.05$ by Student's one-tailed t -test. Error bars show the standard
315 error of the mean (SEM, $n = 6$).

316

317 **Figure 6.** The negative correlations between bit tip surface area (cm^2) and temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at the various
318 skew angles after the 5 min cutting tests. Each spot represents the average value of 6 repeats.

319

320 **Figure 7.** Snapshot image obtained with an IR data processing program. A high temperature ($\sim 564^{\circ}\text{C}$)
321 was generated by the friction between a cutting tool (S1) and rock during rock cutting tests.

322

323 **Figure 8.** The effect of skew angle on bit wear by friction tests for 5 min. *: significantly different from
324 zero (0) skew angle at $P < 0.059$ by Student's one-tailed t -test. Error bars show SEM ($n = 6$).

325

326 **Figure 9.** The effect of skew angle on rock excavation performance by friction tests for 5 min. *:
327 significantly different from zero (0) skew angle at $P < 0.059$ by Student's one-tailed t -test. Error bars
328 show SEM ($n = 6$).

329 **Figure 10.** The correlations between bit weight loss and rock weight loss at the various skew angles after
330 the 5 min cutting tests. Each spot represents the average value of 6 trials.

331

Figure 1. Frictional ignition test machine with rock wheel. (A) Protractor like page aid and (B) Skew angle of cutting tools is adjusted by the protractor like page aid.

Figure 2. Cartoon images for critical angles of cutting bit. A: initial clearance angle, B: attack angle, and C: skew angle.

Figure 3. Engineered conical cutting bits with a 2 g of deviation. B1: BETEK coal cutting bit; B2: BETEK rock cutting bit; S1: Sandvik coal cutting bit; and S2: Sandvik rock cutting bit. The unit is millimeter (mm).

Fig. 4. Snapshot image of IR camera Data Cube Viewer data processing program.

Figure 5. Skew angle effect on bit temperature increment at the 5 min of friction test. Statistically different from zero (D) skew angle at $P < 0.05$ by Student's one-tailed *t*-test. Error bars show standard error of the mean (SEM, $n = 5$).

Figure 6. The negative correlations between bit tip surface area and temperature increment at the various skew angles. Each spot represents the average value of 5 replications.

Fig. 7. Snapshot image of IR camera Data Cube Viewer data processing program.

Figure 8. Skew angle effect on bit wear by friction test for 5 min. *Statistically different from zero (0) skew angle at $P < 0.05$ by Student's one-tailed Test. Error bars show SEM ($n = 6$).

Figure 9. Skew angle effect on rock excavation by friction test for 5 min. *Statistically different from zero (0) skew angle at $P < 0.05$ by Student's one-tailed Test. Error bars show SEM ($n = 6$).

Figure 10. The correlations between bit weight loss and rock weight loss at the various skew angles after 5 min cutting tests. Each spot represents the average value of 6 replications.